

Journal home page:
<http://www.iajpr.com/index.php/en/>

INDO AMERICAN
 JOURNAL OF
 PHARMACEUTICAL
 RESEARCH

DRUG DELIVERY BY VIRUS LIKE PARTICLES

Mohammed Shadul*, Subal Debnath, Santhosh Kumar C, Arghya Acharjee¹, Saurav Nandi¹,

Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vil. Velkatta, Kondapak (mdl),
 Dist. Medak, Siddipet, Andhra Pradesh – 502 277.

¹Aurobindo Pharma Ltd., Maitrivihar, Ameerpet, Hyderabad, A.P.

ARTICLE INFO

Received 10 August 2011
 Received in revised form
 13 August 2011
 Accepted 17 August 2011
 Available online 29 August
 2011.

Keywords

VLPs,
 Polyoma virus
 Virus capsid
 Baculovirus
 Nuclear localization of
 VLPs

ABSTRACT

The drug delivery system described here is based on a virus like particle consisting of the recombinant expressed major capsid protein of Polyomavirus, VP1. Polyoma, a murine virus belonging to the Papovaviridae, forms a non-enveloped icosahedral capsid. These capsids are organized as a double shell composed of three different proteins: VP1, VP2 and VP3. The outer shell of the virus is composed of 360 VP1 molecules arranged as 72 pentamers. These capsids have a diameter of about 50 nm. The VP1 protein acts as a major ligand for certain membrane receptors during virus infection. VLPs have demonstrated their potential in transfecting mammalian cells. In the case of cell transfection, the VLPs are bound to sialic acid residues which are present on almost all cells of higher eukaryotes. To achieve a cell type specific targeting of this potential useful vector system, new functional domains have been established on the surface of VP1. Virus like particles displays an excellent system for drug delivery *in vitro* and *In-vivo*. The diameter of the capsid amounts to approximately 50 nm and whereas the diameter of the pentamers adds up to 8.5 nm. Beyer *et al.* described the great potential of VP1 capsids as heterologous drug carriers, especially for the delivery of foreign protein antigens. VLPs were well suited for evoking a protective immune response on several routes of vaccine administration. Both, humoral and cell-mediated immunity was observed. The prominent advantage of these drug delivery devices was presented by the capacity to target antigenic proteins or DNA vaccines to immature dendritic cells along their maturation pathway. VP1-VLPs are shown to be a useful tool to incorporate not only DNA but also small biological molecules and to improve the specific delivery of these molecules to their target cells.

Corresponding author

Mohammed Shadul

Email: subal_2007@yahoo.co.in

Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vil. Velkatta, Mdl: Kondapak,
 Dist. Medak, Siddipet. Andhra Pradesh – 502 277. Phone: 09640707032.

Please cite this article in press as: Mohammed S *et al.*, Drug Delivery By Virus Like Particles . Indo American Journal of Pharm Research. 2011;1(4):226-234.

INTRODUCTION

Gene therapy is being explored as treatment for human diseases and a number of clinical studies have successfully demonstrated proof of principle. Viral vectors have been widely used in such studies as they are able to deliver genes efficiently and achieve long-term expression. However, viral vectors have the potential for introducing or generating infectious viruses and the immune system rapidly clears modified cells expressing virally encoded gene products. These factors, in conjunction with problems of large-scale production, have driven a search for alternative nonviral delivery systems. One approach being developed uses virus-like particles (VLPs) to deliver genes. VLPs are composed of recombinant structural viral coat proteins, which spontaneously assemble into protein spheres closely resembling the parental virus particle. However as the VLPs do not contain any genetic material they are unable to replicate, and as such are harmless to the person who has been vaccinated. However, that person will now be protected against infection by the real (pathogenic) virus. These characteristics mean that the VLP platform has huge potential for use as an extremely effective anti viral vaccine [1].

However the production of VLPs is not without its problems. In order to produce a functional VLP that effectively mimics real virus good yields of multiple virus structural proteins are needed. These must then be correctly assembled into a particle that reproduces the confirmation of the outer shell (capsid) of an infectious virus. The expression system used to produce the particles must be both safe and capable of producing multiple proteins both on a small scale (for testing) and on a larger scale (for vaccine manufacture). Virus-like particles (VLPs) are virus capsid that lacks the RNA. The capsid is madeup of proteins. It can be imagined as a soccer ball. VLPs have tiny space in them. This space can be loaded with drugs. This research aims to develop a system to load "cargo" inside tiny space of virus capsid and its controlled release at the

required site. The "cargo" can be either a DNA or enzymes or some other compounds (**Fig1**). This field is now in a nascent state but harbor tremendous potential for pharmaceutical industries.

Fig.1: Targeting of virus like particles as a cargo.

Virus-like particles resemble [viruses](#), but are non-infectious because they do not contain any viral genetic material. The expression of viral structural proteins, such as Envelope or Capsid, can result in the self-assembly of virus like particles (VLPs). VLPs derived from the Hepatitis B virus and composed of the small HBV derived surface antigen (HBsAg) were described over 40 years ago from patient sera. More recently, VLPs have been produced from components of a wide variety of virus families including Parvoviridae (e.g. adeno-associated virus), Retroviridae (e.g. HIV), and Flaviviridae (e.g. Hepatitis C virus). VLPs can be produced in a variety of cell culture systems including mammalian cell lines, insect cell lines, yeast, and plant cells.

STRUCTURE ^[1]

Polymaviruses are non-enveloped, double-stranded DNA viruses. Their capsids are composed of three proteins: VP1, VP2, VP3, where VP1 represents the major capsid protein. As the DNA replication of polyomaviruses takes place in the nucleus the capsid, namely the VP1, possesses a nuclear localization signal. The VP1 of different polyomaviruses expressed in heterologous systems forms virus-like particles (VLPs) without need for the minor proteins VP2 and VP3 (**Fig. 2**).

Fig. 2: Computer graphical illustration of VP1 pentamers of the polyomavirus capsid. Figure A displays the surface morphology of the capsid. The diameter of the capsid amounts to approximately 50 nm and whereas the diameter of the pentamers adds up to 8.5 nm. Figure B shows the pentavalent pentamers (a) and the hexavalent pentamers (b).

CELLULAR UPTAKE [2]

Virus particles were taken up by monopinocytotic vesicles through the cell membrane. The virus was enclosed by the membrane and was carried through the cytoplasm to the nucleus. Normally, the native virus is then uncoated and the replication process can begin (productive infection). On the other hand, empty capsids were absorbed as phagocytotic vesicles into the cells and were degraded in lysosomes (non-productive infection). In this case a specific transport to the outer cell membrane could not be observed. The receptor binding is an important attribute for the pathology of the different types of polyomaviruses (Fig 3). For the receptor recognition it seems to be important that N-acetyl neuraminic acid (sialic acid) is presented on the cell surface. The transport of certain proteins to the nucleus has been shown to depend on nuclear localization signal (NLS) sequences residing in the proteins. NLS are highly basic amino acid stretches which were also found in VP1 (Ala1- Cys11) and VP2/3 (Arg301-Pro319). These sequences target the capsid to the nucleus.

Fig. 3: Cellular uptake of virus like particles [2].

PRODUCTION OF VLPs

Expression Systems^[3]

There are different cell lines used for recombinant expression of the structural proteins VP1, VP2 and VP3 of polyomaviruses. Insect cells, *Escherichia coli* and yeast are the mainly used cell types. The structural proteins of murine polyomavirus, JC virus, SV 40, avian polyomavirus and monkey B-lymphatic papovavirus (LPV) have been shown to be expressible in insect cells by a baculovirus vector. Expression of the major structural protein VP1 of JC virus in the insect cell line Sf158 was achieved with the help of recombinant baculoviruses. In place they cloned the genes including the sequences for the VP1, VP2 and VP3 proteins of murine polyomavirus into a p2Bac dual multiple cloning site vector. This vector and the linear DNA of *Autographa californica* multiple nuclear polyhedrosis virus (AcMNPV) are cotransfected into *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Sf9) cells. These cells are now able to express the adequate proteins.

Purification^{[4],[5]}

After lyses of the producing cells and separation of cell constituent's different purification methods can be used to achieve pure recombinant proteins. This cellular lysate can be purified via cesium chloride (CsCl) density gradient centrifugation, whereas purified the protein via chitin affinity chromatography. Another method of purification takes advantage of expression of the protein as a glutathione S-transferase (GST) fusion protein. These fusion proteins can be deterged using affinity chromatography on immobilized glutathione. The cleavage of the fusion proteins from the carrier results from digestion with site-specific proteases. Thrombin or blood coagulation factor Xa can act as sucpoteases. As well purification can be achieved via dialysis and proceeding to a phosphocellulose (P-11) column.

Assembly^[6]

Expressed and purified VP1 monomers immediately accumulate to pentamers. These capsomeres assemble into capsids and polymorphic aggregates by increasing the ionic strength of the solution. To stabilize this virus like particles even at low ionic strength, calcium has to be added. In addition disulfide bonds stabilize the capsids. By the use of a

VP1 mutant with only two of the originally six cysteines (position 19 and 114) it could be shown that only intrapentamer but no interpentamer disulfide bounds were necessary for stabilization and complete virus assembly.

Loading^{[7],[8]}

Barr *et. al.* (1979) described (Fig. 4) for the first time the production of polyoma like particles (PLPs). These particles were composed of purified, empty capsids and polyoma DNA. The DNA uptake was achieved by an osmotic shock. First of all a complex between the empty capsids and the DNA was performed. Afterwards incubation in sterile distilled water at 37°C took place to load the capsids. These particles were stable in high salt concentrations. The integrated double-stranded DNA was protected against pancreatic DNase degradation and the molecular weight amounted to approximately 1.1x10⁶ Dalton. Polyoma virus pseudocapsids are referred to as virus like particles (VLPs) just composed of VP, are able to incorporate exogenous DNA till 3kbp. Not only linear, circular or supercoiled polyoma DNA but also single stranded DNA (antisense oligonucleotides), rRNA and synthetic homopolymers are shown to be encapsulated into VLPs to enhance cellular uptake into cell. To increase the transfer of larger DNA fragments (greater than 3kbp), a possible application could be DNA transfection for gene therapy, and the DNA was complexed with the polycation polylysine. Afterwards these complexes were encapsulated in VLPs to protect the DNA against degradation.

Fig. 4: Loading of VLPs.

Targeting^{[6], [7]}

VLPs have demonstrated their potential in transfecting mammalian cells. In the case of cell transfection, the VLPs are bound to sialic acid residues which are present on almost all cells of higher eukaryotes. To achieve a cell type specific targeting of this potential useful vector system, new functional domains have to be established on the surface of VP1. One attempt is the insertion of single chain Fv fragments, which are the smallest antigen binding antibody fragments. However, this strategy is limited by the modification of the virus coat protein and the development of single chain Fv fragments. Another strategy is the insertion of an immunoglobulin binding domain from *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Therefore as a result, Virus like particles displays an excellent system for drug delivery *In-vitro*. *In-vivo* application turns out to be more difficult. Murine VP1-VLPs causes an antibody response in normal and immunodeficient mice. T-cell independent antiviral IgM and IgG response was tested as well on T-cell deficient mice. These animals were infected with the soluble structural protein VP1, virus like particles and live polyomavirus. IgM response arose from each of the viral antigens, whereas IgG production was only detectable via immunization with the live virus. These properties can be exploited to clone highly immunogenic virus like particles in order to develop new vaccines. The current status of using VLPs as subunit vaccines is described by Noad (2003). There about it is reported that virus like particles mimic the structure of real virus particles without being infectious because of the lack of the pathogenous genome.

GENE TRANSFER BY USING VP1sec VLPs^[9]

VP1sec VLPs were still able to mediate gene expression despite the fact that they appeared less well formed, lack the 86 kDa dimer and were more sensitive to enzymatic degradation. VP1wt and VP1sec cells and VP1sec culture supernatants were partially purified using the scheme developed for isolating VLPs from recombinant baculovirus infected cells. The resulting material was separated on CsCl density gradients and collected fractions analysed for VP1 by Western blotting. High

molecular weight complexes were isolated with buoyant densities similar to empty recombinant baculovirus expressed VLPs.

PRINCIPAL FINDINGS^[10]

1. Polyomavirus-like particles can encapsidate protein ligands: The inner surface of capsids was modified in order to achieve a specific interaction of the capsomeres with the ligands. During *In-vitro* assembly, this interaction results in encapsidation of ligands like proteins and peptides into the forming polyomavirus-like particles. The first WW domain of the mouse Formin binding protein 11 (FBP11) was fused to the NH₂ terminus of VP1 (which faces the interior of the capsid) as a module to facilitate this interaction. WW domains are small protein domains that were named after two conserved tryptophan residues that are essential for maintenance of the native fold and for ligand binding. The FBP11 WW domains specifically bind proline-rich ligands that bear the consensus motif PPLP. Protein modeling studies of the VP1-WW fusion protein revealed there is sufficient space inside the capsid to allow proper folding and arrangement of the WW domains. Given that there are 360 ligand binding sites (72 pentameric VP1 molecules per capsid). It was calculated that 360 globular proteins with an average size of up to 17 kDa could theoretically be encapsidated.

2. VP1-WW capsomeres obtain a native fold and bind PPLP sequences: The fusion protein VP1-WW, expressed and purified from recombinant *Escherichia coli* in a soluble form, was characterized with respect to correct protein folding and ligand binding of the WW domain. To confirm the native fold, far UV circular dichroism spectra of the VP1-WW fusion protein were recorded and compared to the spectrum of the wild-type protein. The VP1-WW spectrum had a significantly increased negative ellipticity difference (De) below 207 nm, indicating an additional portion of b-sheet secondary structure as expected from the addition of the three-stranded anti-parallel b-sheet of the WW domain. The difference spectrum of VP1-WW minus VP1 represents the spectrum of the single WW domain.

3. VP1-WW capsomeres encapsidate PPLP-tagged peptides and proteins during *In-vitro* assembly:

Either fluorescence-labeled PPLP peptides or PPLPtagged green fluorescent protein (GFP) were used as model ligands for optimization of their encapsidation. Encapsidation rates were determined by size exclusion chromatography, which separates virus-like particles from free capsomeres and free ligands (**Fig. 5**). The absorptions of the proteins at 280 nm and of the chromophores at 490 nm and 583 nm, respectively, were recorded simultaneously; after integration of the respective peak areas, the *In-vitro* assembly efficiencies and the encapsidation rates were calculated. It was found that the maximum encapsidation rate was 230 peptide molecules and 260 GFP molecules per virus like particle.

Fig. 5: *In vitro* assembly and ligand encapsidation of VP1-WW. Size exclusion chromatography profiles show that capsids contain the model ligands, either fluorescence-labeled PPLP peptide (a) or GFP (c). Electron micrographs reveal a homogeneous population of PPLP peptide (b) or GFP (d) containing capsids that are indistinguishable from wild-type capsids.

4. Model peptides and proteins are efficiently delivered into NIH 3T3 cells:

The ability of polyomavirus-like particles to transfer encapsidated molecules into eukaryotic cells was examined in tissue cultures *In-vitro*. Cultures of NIH 3T3 mouse fibroblasts were incubated with virus-like particles containing either fluorescence-labeled peptides or PPLP-tagged GFP and subsequently analyzed using confocal laser scanning microscopy. Significant fluorescence was detected within all cells even after 30 min incubation time. The fluorescent molecules were localized near the cellular membrane and eventually were distributed more throughout the entire cells with longer incubation times, indicating that encapsidated ligands were rapidly and efficiently delivered. To determine the distribution of capsids and encapsidated ligands individually, the capsid protein VP1 was labeled with a different fluorescence dye at a specific cysteine residue in addition to the fluorescent ligands. During uptake experiments into NIH 3T3 cells, the capsid proteins and ligands could be clearly detected and distinguished. Within the time frame of the experiments, most of the ligands were still colocalized with the capsid proteins (**Fig. 6**).

Fig. 6: Delivery of fluorescence-labeled PPLP peptide into NIH 3T3 cells. a) The peptide-loaded particles are found mainly in the membrane area and the outer cytoplasm. b) After further incubation, the particles migrate mainly into the cytoplasm and are in part taken up into lysosomes, which results in yellow staining due to the co-localization of blue (lysosomes) and green (ligand inside capsids) dyes. Differential staining of capsids (c), ligands (d), and lysosomes (f, blue) reveals co-localization of ligands and capsids (e) and partial uptake of the loaded capsids into lysosomes (f).

Fig. 7: Schematic diagram of peptide/protein delivery using virus-like particles. All components are produced separately, including the PPLP-tagged therapeutic peptide or protein (*a*), VP1-WW capsomeres (*b*), and VP1 capsomeres with additional functions (*c*)—for example, sequences to target the assembled particles to specific cellular receptors. The components are then mixed and virus-like particles are generated by in vitro assembly, yielding tailored therapeutics.

CONCLUSIONS

With an increasing understanding of the pathogenesis of many diseases at a molecular level, it is possible to use recombinant proteins for the functional substitution of defective or missing proteins or for the modulation of metabolic or signal transduction pathways. However, most proteins are unable to enter cells and reach intracellular targets, and are therefore limited to extracellular applications. Recently, fusions of target proteins with viral protein sequences of the HIV TAT and the Herpes simplex virus VP22 were found to mediate transfer of the target protein across the plasma membrane into cells. In a novel approach, we used polyomavirus-like particles that are able to enter mammalian cells for the delivery of peptides and proteins. The outer capsid protein VP1 can be expressed and purified from recombinant *E. coli* and spontaneously forms virus-like particles *In-vitro* in the presence of Ca²⁺ ions without the need for VP2 or VP3. The major focus of the present study was the directed encapsidation of model ligands into the particles.

Cell culture experiments demonstrated an efficient uptake of the vector and the delivery of the encapsidated substances. There is approximately an equal distribution of the ligands within the cytoplasm and ligands remaining in endosomes. The drug delivery system presented here should be applicable in general for the delivery of a wide range of peptides, small PPLP-tagged compounds, and

proteins. Possible limitations for the encapsidation of proteins could arise for large proteins, which may decrease the *In-vitro* assembly of the capsids due to steric hindrance. Compared to fusion proteins with viral sequences, encapsidation into virus-like particles has the advantage that the ligands are protected inside a stable protein shell from external proteases. The strategy of mixed capsid assembly may also be exploited to combine different functions within the vector (**Fig. 7**). For example, capsomeres that facilitate encapsidation of the ligands could be combined with capsomeres modified on the outer surface so as to allow targeting of specific cell types. It is also possible to fuse other WW domains to the VP1 capsomeres that recognize different proline-rich sequences. During *In-vitro* assembly with varying VP1-WW fusion capsomeres, different ligands could be encapsidated and administered simultaneously with an exactly defined ratio. For example, emerging resistance of tumor tissue to a single drug could be circumvented by applying a mixture of diverse drugs. In summary, it is envisaged that engineered virus-like particles as a basis of a modular delivery system may greatly enhance the use of therapeutic peptides and recombinant proteins. Such multifunctional drug delivery systems may be useful for treating human diseases. Future studies will focus on the delivery of biologically active compounds and their distribution and effects in tissue and animal models.

REFERENCES

1. Christiane Georgens, Jorg Weyermann1 and Andreas Zimmer's, Recombinant Virus like Particles as Drug Delivery System. Current Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, 2005, 6: 49-55.
2. Griffith GR, Marriott SJ, Rintoul DA and Consigli RA, cell penetration and trafficking of polyomavirus *Virus Res.*, 1988, 10(1): 41-51.
3. Salunke DM, Caspar DL and Garcea RL, Polymorphism in the assembly of polyomavirus capsid protein VP1, *Cell*, 1986, 46(6): 895-904.
4. Gillock ET, Rottinghaus S, Chang D, Cai X, Smiley SA, An K. and Consigli R A, Polyomavirus major capsid protein VP1 is capable of packaging cellular DNA when expressed in the baculovirus system. *J Virol.*, 1997, 71(4): 2857-65.
5. An K; Smiley SA, Gillock ET, Reeves WM and Consigli RA, Avian polyomavirus major capsid protein VP1 interacts with the minor capsid proteins and is transported into the cell nucleus but does not assemble into capsid-like particles when expressed in the baculovirus system. *Virus Res.*, 1999, 64(2): 173-85.
6. Braun H, Boller K, Lower J, Bertling WM and Zimmer A. Mechanism of Assembly of Recombinant Murine Polyomavirus-Like Particles, *Biotechnol. Appl. Biochem.*, 1999, 29: 31-43.
7. Henke S, Rohmann A, Bertling WM, Dingermann T and Zimmer A, Enhanced in vitro oligonucleotide and plasmid DNA transport by VP1 virus-like particles. *Pharm. Research news*, 2000, 17(9): 1062-70.
8. Slilaty S N, Berns KI, and Aposhian HVJ, Formation of Polyomavirus-Like Particles with Different VP, *Biol. Chem.*, 1982, 257(11): 6571-5.
9. Krauzewicz N, S tokrova J, Jenkins C, Elliott, M, Higgins CF and Griffin BE, Virus-like gene transfer into cells mediated by polyoma virus pseudocapsids. *Gene Ther*, 2000, 7: 2122-2231.
10. Uli Schmidt, Constanze Gu Nther, Rainer Rudolph and Gerald Bohm, Protein and peptide delivery via engineered polyomavirus-like particles. *The FASEB Journal*. 2001, 15: 1648.

